

Low-rank attention augmented Gaussian processes for multivariate data analysis

Oluwole Oyebamiji¹, Dilum Dissanayake², Muhammed Cavus¹

¹School of Computer Science, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK,

²School of Geography, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK

³Faculty of Engineering and Environment, Northumbria University, Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK

Abstract: We have developed an efficient low-rank attention-augmented Gaussian processes (LAAGP) model that effectively combines accuracy with a reduction in the computational costs associated with transformer attention and Gaussian processes (GP). This model addresses the limitations of standard GP models, such as poor covariance function expressiveness for long-range multivariate forecasting and inadequate data representation capacity. LAAGP is a powerful forecasting technique that integrates the transformer self-attention mechanism with GP. The framework features a transformer encoder that processes the input embeddings to extract essential information, using positional and variable encoding along with relative embeddings to enhance attention scores. The GP decoder, known for its flexibility and reliable uncertainty estimates, has been adapted to predict the system’s evolution over time. This enhancement allows the model to achieve a balance between computational efficiency, predictive accuracy, and uncertainty quantification, thereby improving performance on intricate tasks like long-range predictions. Our model has been evaluated on several benchmark regression and classification datasets.

1. Introduction

A Gaussian Process (GP) is a powerful tool in machine learning and statistics used for probabilistic modelling [1]. Their non-parametric form, analytical properties, and ability to model uncertainty are useful in machine learning. However, they are affected by limitations, particularly their significant computational and storage cost and kernel expressiveness. Sparse GPs (SGPs) [2,3] attempt to address computational and storage costs. Several methods have been proposed along this line of research, each with its advantages and limitations. While SGPs and other variational techniques [3–5] have addressed the problem of computational costs, GPs are still not suitable for many applications due to their reliance on kernel or covariance functions having limited expressiveness. The covariance function is the crucial ingredient in a GP regression and is defined as the similarity between input points, as it encodes our assumptions about the function which we wish to learn, such as smoothness, periodicity, or stationarity. The choice of kernel affects the performance of a GP on a given task [6]. Standard kernels such as radial basis function (RBF), Matern etc can only model the types of functions encoded in their structure. Unlike deep neural networks, they do not learn hierarchical representations from data thus struggle to capture complex input-output relationships, especially in high-dimensional inputs [7–9].

These functions are most frequently employed with fairly straightforward distance metrics. Therefore, in some applications, applying different similarity metrics across various regions of the input space may be necessary. One approach to this challenge would be stacking GPs, similar to the stacking of Perceptrons in a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [10]. However, arranging GPs so that the output from one layer feeds into the next increases non-linearity and makes the inference analytically intractable. Such methodologies are generally classified as DGPs [11]. DGPs provide a powerful framework for Bayesian machine learning, offering increased flexibility and better uncertainty estimation [11,12]. Other proposed techniques to address expressiveness limitations are learned kernels using Deep Kernel Learning (DKL) [13,14], which combines a

neural network with a GP and using attention mechanisms or transformers to learn more expressive, input-adaptive kernel structures [9]. To scale up GP to handle large datasets and offer high expressivity, we propose a new scalable attention-based GP model by augmenting GP with a low-rank attention. We proposed an end-to-end deep learning model that incorporates the Multi-output Gaussian Process to quantify uncertainty in high-dimensional data, together with a transformer attention for prediction tasks. We also used an alternative closed-form objective function, α -ELBO, to enhance parameter estimation in the augmented GP, relying on the Rényi α -divergence. Our case studies cover a wide range of applications.

2. Related works

GPs are probabilistic models that excel in uncertainty quantification and have been widely used in many application areas [15, 16]. However, they scale poorly with large data and struggle with high-dimensional inputs. On the other hand, transformers [17] are powerful deep learning models capable of learning long-range dependencies efficiently using self-attention. Combining GPs with a transformer architecture aims to blend the strengths of both worlds, the uncertainty modelling and interpretability of GPs with the scalability and representational power of transformers. For example, in the works of [13, 14], a deep neural network learns representations which are then passed into a GP framework. The approach involves mapping input sequences to embeddings and applying a GP over these embeddings for prediction with uncertainty.

[18] introduced the attention GP (AGP) model, a novel probabilistic attention mechanism based on GPs for deep multiple instance learning (MIL). The probabilistic nature of AGP enhances robustness to overfitting, especially on small datasets, and allows for end-to-end training. [19] proposed the attentive GP, which combines an attention-based network with GP regression for probabilistic time-series generation. This model addresses the computational demands and uncertainty underestimation associated with recurrent networks by dispensing with recurrence and convolutions.

In contrast, [20] addressed limitations in previous approaches that integrated GPs into transformers by proposing the correlated Gaussian process transformer (CGPT). Existing techniques usually required symmetric attention to satisfy the symmetric requirements of GP kernels, reducing the model’s representation capacity. The CGPT models self-attention units as cross-covariance between two correlated GPs, allowing for asymmetries in attention and enhancing representation capacity.

The integration of attention mechanisms into GPs has led to significant advancements in modelling capabilities, particularly in handling complex data structures and providing robust uncertainty quantification. The reviewed works demonstrate that attention-augmented GPs can outperform traditional models in various applications, offering improved performance, scalability, and interpretability. We note that despite the advantage combining transformer and GP introduces dual bottlenecks, quadratic attention and cubic GP scaling. In this work, we focus on further enhancing these models’ scalability and exploring applications in various domains by introducing a scalable transformer that uses singular value decomposition of attention matrices.

3. Background

This section starts with an overview of GP models, its parameter estimation, predictive distribution and Rényi α -divergence. Traditional GPs often struggle to effectively capture the intricate and hierarchical nature of large datasets. To overcome this challenge, we shall integrate transformer attention with GPs, resulting in more flexible and expressive models.

3.1. Gaussian processes

A collection of random variables is called a Gaussian Process(GP) if the joint distribution of any finite subset of its variables is a Gaussian. GPs are Gaussian distributions defined as probabilistic mappings from an input data space to its output label space [16]. Suppose the training data input-output pairs are given in matrices $\mathbf{X} \in \mathcal{R}^{N \times Q}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathcal{R}^{N \times D}$ respectively, and the plan is to estimate the unobserved, latent function $f = f(\mathbf{x})$, for generating \mathbf{Y} given \mathbf{X} . Gaussian processes (GPs) can be defined as nonparametric

prior distributions over the latent function f . Let

$$\mathbf{y}_n = f(\mathbf{x}_n) + \epsilon_n, \quad \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I}),$$

where f is drawn from a Gaussian process, i.e. $f(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(\mathbf{0}, k(x, x'))$. This zero-mean Gaussian process prior only depends on the covariance function k through the inputs \mathbf{X} . Define $\mathbf{F} = \{\mathbf{f}_n\}_n^N$, as the collection of latent function which is normally distributed, then we can analytically computed the marginal likelihood where $\mathbf{K}_{NN} = k(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})$ is the full covariance matrix and σ_ϵ^2 is the observation noise. The GP priors can be similarly given as $p(\mathbf{F} | \mathbf{X}) = \prod_{d=1}^D \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{f}_d | \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{K}_{NN})$ which is also Gaussian allowing for general non-linear mappings to be marginalised out analytically to obtain the likelihood although which is computationally expensive for large datasets.

$$\mathbb{L}_{\text{exact}} = p(\mathbf{Y} | \mathbf{X}) = \prod_{d=1}^D \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_d | \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{K}_{NN} + \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I}). \quad (3.1)$$

3.2. Sparse GPs

Stochastic variational inference (SVI) allows VI for very large data sets, implementing through inducing point methods, usually by optimising an evidence lower bound (ELBO) based on Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [21, 22]. Consider a stochastic function $f : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, given a likelihood $p(y | f)$ and observations $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_N)^\top$ at design locations $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N)^\top$. A GP prior can be assigned to the function f , modelling all function values as joint Gaussian, characterised by a covariance function $k : \mathbb{R}^D \times \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a mean function $m : \mathbb{R}^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Similarly, let us define a variable $\mathbf{u} = f(\mathbf{Z})$, and for a set of \mathcal{M} inducing locations $\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_M)^\top$, and let $\mathbf{f} = f(\mathbf{X})$ denotes the function values at the design points. The expressions $[m(\mathbf{X})]_i = m(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $[k(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z})]_{ij} = k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)$ represent the joint density $p(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u})$, which is Gaussian in nature. The mean of this density is derived from the mean function evaluated at every input $(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z})^\top$, with the corresponding covariance being obtainable as well [11, 23]. Given that the joint GP prior $p(f, \mathbf{u}; \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) = p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{u}; \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}) \times p(\mathbf{u})$, the joint density of \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{u} can be defined as

$$p(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}) = \underbrace{p(\mathbf{f} | \mathbf{u}; \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z})}_{\text{GP prior}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^N p(y_i | f_i)}_{\text{likelihood}}.$$

Inference in the joint density presented above can be performed in closed form when the likelihood is Gaussian, although the computational complexity increases cubically with N . We can implement variational inference to approximate the posterior distribution $q(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u})$ by minimising the Kullback-Leibler divergence $\text{KL}[q || p]$. This process is equivalent to maximising the lower bound of the marginal likelihood (evidence): $\mathbb{L} = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u})} \left[\log \frac{p(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u})}{q(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u})} \right]$, which is given as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{svgp}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \left\{ \log \mathcal{N}(y_i | \mu_f(\mathbf{x}_i), \sigma_{\text{obs}}^2) - \frac{\Sigma_f(\mathbf{x}_i)}{2\sigma_{\text{obs}}^2} \right\} - \text{KL}(q(\mathbf{u}) || p(\mathbf{u})), \quad (3.2)$$

where $\mu_f(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the predictive mean function given by $\mu_f(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{k}_i^T \mathbf{K}_{MM}^{-1} m$ and $\Sigma_f(\mathbf{x}_i) \equiv \text{Var}[f_i | \mathbf{x}_i]$ denotes the latent function variance $\Sigma_f(\mathbf{x}_i) = \tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{ii} + \mathbf{k}_i^T \mathbf{K}_{MM}^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{K}_{MM}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_i$, and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{svgp}}$ which depends on $m, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{Z}, \sigma_{\text{obs}}$ and the various kernel hyperparameters θ_{ker} can be maximised with gradient methods. Further details is given in Appendix A1. The lower bound for VI is given as

$$\mathcal{L}_{VI} = \log \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{Q}) - \frac{1}{2\sigma_\epsilon^2} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{K}_{N,N} - \mathbf{Q}), \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{K}_{N,U} \mathbf{K}_{U,U}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{U,N}$ is a low-rank approximation of the exact covariance matrix $\mathbf{K}_{N,N}$ and \mathbf{U} is a collection of latent variables.

3.3. Renyi α -divergence

The selection of the appropriate inference method remains unclear, as it is dependent on the data. Rainforth [24] poses a significant inquiry concerning variational and exact inference. Empirical evidence indicates that

a tighter bound can, at times, impede learning by reducing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Similarly, the ELBO is predicated on KL divergence, and its asymmetry tends to underestimate posterior uncertainty, potentially leading to overconfident predictions as noted in the works of [23, 25]. Attempt to tighten ELBO could also result in overfitting. Moreover, exact inference in GPs is only manageable for small datasets due to its $O(N^3)$ complexity. Rényi α -divergence provides an alternative inference technique, an α -ELBO, that generalises the KL divergence and provides a controllable trade-off between the exact and variational inferences [26, 27]. This is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_\alpha = \log \left\{ \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_\epsilon^2 \mathbf{I} + (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{K}_{N,N} + \alpha \mathbf{Q}) \right\} + \log \left| \mathbf{I} + \frac{1 - \alpha}{\sigma_\epsilon^2} (\mathbf{K}_{N,N} - \mathbf{Q}) \right|^{\frac{-\alpha}{2(1-\alpha)}}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{K}_{N,U} \mathbf{K}_{U,U}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{U,N}$ and $|\cdot|$ is a determinant operator, \mathcal{L}_α can be viewed as the convex combination of equations 3.1 and 3.3 and controlled by the tuning parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1)$. The tuning parameter determines the shape and tightness of the variational lower bound. Further details is provided in the Appendix.

3.4. Rényi GPs

Standard VI minimises the KL divergence between the variational density $q(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ and the intractable posterior $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y})$. This minimisation problem produces a tractable ELBO for the marginal log-likelihood function of the data $\log p(\mathbf{y})$. As noted earlier, the Rényi's α -divergence serves as a more general distance measure than the KL divergence and thus could be applied to \mathcal{GP} . Therefore, using the Rényi divergence measure, a lower bound on the marginal likelihood is given in (3.4). We note that this lower bound is a convex combination of components derived from sparse GP(\mathbf{Q}) and exact GP($\mathbf{K}_{N,N}$). The parameter α controls the shape and smoothness of the lower bound. Also, \mathcal{L}_α is decreasing on $\alpha \in [0, 1)$. As $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, we can recover the well-known ELBO of GP in the standard VI [28]. According to [27], the exact component $\mathbf{K}_{N,N}$ in (3.4) is computationally expensive to optimise. A recently proposed efficient algorithm based on Blackbox Matrix-Matrix multiplication [5, 29] has been used to overcome this problem. This algorithm uses various iterative methods such as conjugate gradient (CG), pivoted Cholesky decomposition and parallel computing. Examining (3.4) reveals that its computational complexity is primarily influenced by the first term, which shares complexity with the exact GP. To estimate the unknown parameters, (3.4) can be rewritten as

$$\mathcal{L}_\alpha(q; \mathbf{y}) = \log |2\pi \boldsymbol{\Psi}|^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{y}^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{y} + \log C_x, \quad (3.5)$$

and the gradient can be computed as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_\alpha(q; \mathbf{y})}{d\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{y}^T \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1} \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Psi}}{d\boldsymbol{\theta}} \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{y} - \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \left(\boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1} \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Psi}}{d\boldsymbol{\theta}} \right) - \frac{\alpha}{2(1-\alpha)} \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{A}^{-1} \frac{d\mathbf{A}}{d\boldsymbol{\theta}} \right). \quad (3.6)$$

Further details are provided in [27] and [26, 30].

3.5. Transformer models

Transformers [17, 31] represent robust neural network architectures that have transformed machine learning across various domains, particularly in natural language processing (NLP) [32], advanced machine translation [33], time series forecasting, and image generation [34]. Pre-trained models based on transformers can be adapted to new tasks efficiently, even with minimal supervision. The core component of the transformer is the attention mechanism, which models complex dependencies between the elements of each input sequence. However, the standard training and inference processes for these transformer architectures scale quadratically with the length of input sequences, which can be excessively large for many applications. Sparse attention [35] mechanisms present a promising way to tackle these issues, as they cut down on the number of computations while maintaining the model's effectiveness. Many existing methods utilise sparsity [36] or low-rank assumptions in the attention matrix to lower costs, though this often compromises expressiveness [37–40].

3.6. Transformer attention

Attention mechanism was introduced by [41,42] and has become the core building block for Transformer models. Attention computes a weighted sum of input values, where the weights or attention scores are derived from a similarity function between a query and a set of keys. This framework was significantly advanced by the transformer architecture [17], which relies entirely on self-attention mechanisms. The attention mechanism not only improves performance on a wide range of tasks but also provides interpretability by highlighting which parts of the input influence the model’s predictions. Let an input sequence $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ be defined as n d -dimensional vectors, then the input \mathbf{X} can be linearly transformed into the query \mathbf{Q} , the key \mathbf{K} , and the value \mathbf{V} matrices, such that

$$\mathbf{Q} \triangleq [\mathbf{q}_1, \mathbf{q}_2, \dots, \mathbf{q}_n]^\top = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W}_q^\top, \quad (3.7)$$

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq [\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_2, \dots, \mathbf{k}_n]^\top = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W}_k^\top, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\mathbf{V} \triangleq [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n]^\top = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{W}_v^\top, \quad (3.9)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_q, \mathbf{W}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times d}$ and $\mathbf{W}_v \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times d}$ are weight matrices. Each tuple of vectors $\{\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{k}_i, \mathbf{v}_i\}_{i=1}^n$ comprise respectively the key, query and value vectors. Similarly, given \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{V} matrices, the final output of the attention is given as

$$\mathbf{A} = \text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^\top}{\sqrt{d}}\right) \cdot \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{V}, \quad (3.10)$$

where the softmax operator is applied to each row of the matrix $\mathbf{H} = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^\top}{\sqrt{d}}\right)$ [20, 43].

4. Experiments

We assess the proposed hybrid LAAGP method on a diverse set of regression datasets from the UCI repository, including Bike, Elevators, Energy, Protein, 3Droad, Song, and Jura. The properties of each dataset evaluated across a diverse range of data are presented in Table 1. Also, we reconstruct structured images and analyse human motion, which includes extracting orientation from face patches and recovering the magnitude of handwritten digits, as reported in [13, 44]. Our goal is to qualitatively evaluate how the models handle uncertainty during training with incomplete data in structured inputs. We utilise 15000 training samples from the MNIST digits dataset [45, 46], incorporating various percentages of randomly missing pixels from each digit. Each image has 768 pixels, yielding a 768-dimensional data space. Similarly, the image dataset [47] comprises 2000 images of a face, captured from sequential frames of a brief video. Each image is 20x28 pixels, resulting in a 560-dimensional data space.

4.1. Results

This section describes the process involved in the evaluation of the experiment. The data is partitioned in an 80%-20% ratio for training and testing. The results are obtained by training models on a defined set of training data and assessing their performance on a specified set of testing data. The experiments are conducted over a total of 500 epochs. The models considered, along with their variations, include Deep Gaussian processes (DGPs), and standard GPs. The DGP model is implemented using GPyTorch and employs a Matern covariance function with independent length scales designated for each input dimension [5, 48]. The marginal log-likelihood is maximised using the Adam optimiser [49]. The DGP models have 3-hidden layers with 50 MC samples.

Figure 1 illustrates the results of evaluating the performance of LAAGP models on image reconstruction tasks where a significant portion of the pixels are missing. It demonstrates the LAAGP model ability to reconstruct corrupted images. The model is trained on images with large areas of missing pixels (30% - 60%) and predicts the original image. For all four datasets (Brendan faces, CIFAR10, MNIST, NDVI), the reconstructed images in the third row are clearly reproduced and are much closer to the original ground truth than the masked images. In Table 2, we observe that the LAAGP model produces good results on the

BRENDAN dataset, with the lowest error (RMSE, MAE) and the best image quality scores (high PSNR, high SSIM). This suggests the model is particularly well-suited for this type of structured, facial data. The MNIST and CIFAR10 datasets show moderate reconstruction errors. However, the extremely high and variable NLL values indicate that the model uncertainty estimates are very poor for these tasks. The very low SSIM for CIFAR10 (0.040) suggests that the reconstructed images, while having the right colours, lack the correct structural details. The NDVI satellite imagery dataset has the highest reconstruction errors (RMSE, MAE) and the worst PSNR, indicating it was the most challenging task for the model.

Figure 1. We assessed the performance of LAAGP models on different datasets. Panel (a) depicts the Brendan faces reconstruction task with 60% of the pixels missing. Panel (b) illustrates the CIFAR10 dataset with 10% of the pixels missing. Panel (c) presents the MNIST reconstruction task, where the digits were trained on partially observed images with 30% of the pixels missing. Panel (d) displays NDVI satellite images with 60% of the pixels missing. In each panel, the first row represents the ground truth data (original), the middle row shows the masked dataset with a certain percentage of pixels missing, and the third row depicts the reconstruction from the LAAGP models with α set to 0.99, respectively.

Table 3 presents benchmark results on the UCI regression dataset, comparing LAAGP performance with that of other methods. The evaluation metrics include Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The table lists performance scores for models such as LAAGP, DGP-Chol, DGP-MF, ODSVGP, SVGP, and PPGPR across various datasets, including 3droad, Bike, Elevators, Energy, Jura, and Protein. Lower NLL and MAE generally indicate better performance. For the Bike dataset in Table 3, DGP-Chol achieves the lowest RMSE at 0.053, but LAAGP significantly outperforms it in NLL with a much more negative value of -2.771. This indicates that while DGP-Chol predictions are closer on average, LAAGP delivers much better-calibrated uncertainty estimates for this dataset. On the Protein dataset, PPGPR-OD has the best RMSE at 0.595 but ranks poorly in NLL at 1.216, pointing to weak uncertainty quantification. LAAGP demonstrates strong performance, especially in NLL scores (e.g., best on Bike, Elevators, Energy) and often on RMSE/MAE (e.g., best RMSE on Bike, Energy, Elevators). This shows it is a highly robust model for probabilistic prediction. DGP-MF and DGP-Chol also perform well on the Bike dataset in terms of RMSE. Using the NLL metric, PPGPR-Chol performs better on Jura and Protein. It is clear that ODSVGP and PPGPR-OD tend to have higher RMSE and MAE across most datasets, indicating they may be less accurate in their point predictions for these tasks.

5. Conclusion

We introduced a novel method for uncertainty analysis using a hybrid Gaussian process transformer based on a low-rank attention-augmented GP. Our experiments span various datasets, including UCI regression data with structured images and human motion analysis, such as extracting face patch orientations and measuring handwritten digit magnitudes. Our goal is to qualitatively evaluate how models handle uncertainty with

Table 1. Summary of regression data used for the analysis. The number of inducing point, learning rate, number of MC samples and number of iterations are set at 128, 0.01, 50, and 500 respectively. All DGP models have three hidden layers.

	Dataset	Elevators	Bike	Protein	3droad	Jura	Energy
Total samples (N)	12449	13034	34297	326155	359	19735	
output dimension (m)	1	1	1	1	3	1	
Batch size	1024	1024	1024	2048	128	1024	

Table 2. Summary of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Negative Loglikelihood (NLL) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for all models and classification dataset average across different levels of α .

	MNIST	CIFAR10	BRENDAN	NDVI
RMSE	0.261 ± 0.003	0.250 ± 0.005	0.116 ± 0.050	0.297 ± 0.013
MAE	0.152 ± 0.002	0.207 ± 0.005	0.085 ± 0.050	0.245 ± 0.010
NLL	93.789 ± 60.149	123.243 ± 47.615	0.574 ± 1.565	14.43 ± 12.954
PSNR	11.673 ± 0.095	12.059 ± 0.182	19.029 ± 1.823	10.542 ± 0.308
SSIM	0.368 ± 0.005	0.040 ± 0.004	0.490 ± 0.070	0.249 ± 0.027

incomplete structured data. The model is tested on images with missing pixels at rates of 60%, 30%, and 10%. Our findings show that using enough samples to estimate expectations leads to convergence and effective uncertainty quantification. The LAAGP model often outperforms other methods on various benchmarks, likely due to its higher approximation flexibility. Also, we expanded our approach to explore different variational inference techniques for estimating GP and DGP parameters. For instance, DSPP experiments used only the mean-field covariance approximation. We examined the impact of applying full Cholesky decomposition of the covariance function to improve optimisation and evaluated other variational methods, including ODGP and SVGP approximations (baseline models). The LAAGP model performs well on structured, simpler datasets like BRENDAN, producing accurate and well-calibrated reconstructions, while its performance is inconsistent on complex natural images such as CIFAR10 and NDVI data, where it struggles to reconstruct fine details and provide reliable uncertainty estimates, despite producing visually recognisable outputs. High NLL values suggest a calibration weakness in the model for specific data types. We observe that no single model outperforms all others across every dataset and metric. The best model often relies on the particular features of the dataset.

Table 3. Summary of the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Negative Loglikelihood (NLL) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for all models and regression dataset average across different levels of α .

Dataset Model	3droad	Bike	Elevators	Energy	Jura	Protein
LAAGP	0.452 ± 0.007	0.107 ± 0.004	0.342 ± 0.000	0.041 ± 0.002	0.714 ± 0.001	0.620 ± 0.010
DGP-Chol*	0.55 ± 0.001	0.088 ± 0.003	0.351 ± 0.001	0.072 ± 0.002	0.698 ± 0.007	0.743 ± 0.005
DGP-MF*	0.476 ± 0.004	0.098 ± 0.003	0.354 ± 0.001	0.081 ± 0.004	0.773 ± 0.006	0.73 ± 0.003
DGP-Chol	0.446 ± 0.006	0.053 ± 0.005	0.352 ± 0.001	0.277 ± 0.003	0.714 ± 0.007	0.75 ± 0.003
DGP-MF	0.466 ± 0.009	0.050 ± 0.006	0.35 ± 0.001	0.064 ± 0.001	0.767 ± 0.005	0.728 ± 0.004
ODSVGP	0.663 ± 0.008	0.24 ± 0.002	0.399 ± 0.001	0.213 ± 0.004	0.642 ± 0.001	0.788 ± 0.003
SVGP	0.500 ± 0.003	0.208 ± 0.005	0.394 ± 0.002	0.13 ± 0.018	0.647 ± 0.004	0.737 ± 0.006
PPGPR-OD	0.688 ± 0.008	0.224 ± 0.001	0.393 ± 0.001	0.221 ± 0.001	0.595 ± 0.002	0.817 ± 0.002
PPGPR-Chol	0.561 ± 0.002	0.273 ± 0.002	0.419 ± 0.002	0.22 ± 0.001	0.624 ± 0.001	0.733 ± 0.005
NLL						
LAAGP	-0.042 ± 0.032	-2.771 ± 0.076	0.305 ± 0.006	-1.892 ± 0.022	3.200 ± 0.100	0.384 ± 0.021
DGP-Chol*	0.418 ± 0.01	-2.673 ± 0.055	0.355 ± 0.002	-1.552 ± 0.022	2.366 ± 0.063	1.062 ± 0.008
DGP-MF*	0.304 ± 0.019	-2.657 ± 0.026	0.361 ± 0.002	-1.258 ± 0.055	3.139 ± 0.042	1.034 ± 0.003
DGP-Chol	0.615 ± 0.013	-1.536 ± 0.106	0.375 ± 0.002	0.400 ± 0.009	3.239 ± 0.024	1.139 ± 0.008
DGP-MF	0.657 ± 0.018	-1.575 ± 0.108	0.37 ± 0.002	-1.337 ± 0.023	3.51 ± 0.02	1.102 ± 0.006
ODSVGP	1.01 ± 0.013	-0.009 ± 0.009	0.551 ± 0.008	-0.02 ± 0.026	3.166 ± 0.016	1.181 ± 0.004
SVGP	0.733 ± 0.006	0.107 ± 0.033	0.521 ± 0.017	-0.513 ± 0.099	2.687 ± 0.037	1.118 ± 0.007
PPGPR-OD	0.939 ± 0.026	-0.371 ± 0.029	0.486 ± 0.002	-0.159 ± 0.011	2.766 ± 0.046	1.216 ± 0.002
PPGPR-Chol	0.459 ± 0.006	-1.755 ± 0.023	0.391 ± 0.003	-1.111 ± 0.011	2.035 ± 0.009	0.96 ± 0.008
MAE						
LAAGP	0.304 ± 0.007	0.031 ± 0.002	0.263 ± 0.001	0.029 ± 0.001	0.444 ± 0.001	0.455 ± 0.013
DGP-Chol*	0.383 ± 0.001	0.029 ± 0.002	0.269 ± 0.001	0.048 ± 0.001	0.435 ± 0.004	0.576 ± 0.005
DGP-MF*	0.330 ± 0.003	0.030 ± 0.001	0.272 ± 0.001	0.059 ± 0.003	0.543 ± 0.005	0.570 ± 0.004
DGP-Chol	0.324 ± 0.005	0.029 ± 0.003	0.269 ± 0.001	0.202 ± 0.002	0.501 ± 0.005	0.595 ± 0.004
DGP-MF	0.339 ± 0.007	0.030 ± 0.003	0.267 ± 0.001	0.049 ± 0.001	0.544 ± 0.004	0.568 ± 0.004
ODSVGP	0.501 ± 0.010	0.158 ± 0.002	0.304 ± 0.001	0.152 ± 0.003	0.458 ± 0.001	0.649 ± 0.003
SVGP	0.359 ± 0.003	0.118 ± 0.004	0.301 ± 0.001	0.099 ± 0.012	0.443 ± 0.004	0.594 ± 0.006
PPGPR-OD	0.523 ± 0.008	0.133 ± 0.001	0.301 ± 0.001	0.159 ± 0.001	0.435 ± 0.003	0.676 ± 0.002
PPGPR-Chol	0.394 ± 0.002	0.096 ± 0.001	0.306 ± 0.001	0.126 ± 0.001	0.421 ± 0.001	0.574 ± 0.005

References

- [1] O. Oyebamiji, D. Wilkinson, P. Jayathilake, T. Curtis, S. Rushton, B. Li, and P. Gupta, “Gaussian process emulation of an individual-based model simulation of microbial communities,” *Journal of Computational Science*, vol. 22, pp. 69–84, 2017.
- [2] M. Titsias, “Variational learning of inducing variables in sparse gaussian processes,” in *Artificial intelligence and statistics*, pp. 567–574, PMLR, 2009.
- [3] A. G. d. G. Matthews, J. Hensman, R. Turner, and Z. Ghahramani, “On sparse variational methods and the kullback-leibler divergence between stochastic processes,” in *Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 231–239, PMLR, 2016.
- [4] D. M. Blei, A. Kucukelbir, and J. D. McAuliffe, “Variational inference: A review for statisticians,” *Journal of the American statistical Association*, vol. 112, no. 518, pp. 859–877, 2017.
- [5] J. Gardner, G. Pleiss, K. Q. Weinberger, D. Bindel, and A. G. Wilson, “Gpytorch: Blackbox matrix-matrix gaussian process inference with gpu acceleration,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 31, 2018.
- [6] A. Wilson and R. Adams, “Gaussian process kernels for pattern discovery and extrapolation,” in *International conference on machine learning*, pp. 1067–1075, PMLR, 2013.
- [7] G. Parra and F. Tobar, “Spectral mixture kernels for multi-output gaussian processes,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [8] S. Remes, M. Heinonen, and S. Kaski, “Non-stationary spectral kernels,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [9] K. Krauth, E. V. Bonilla, K. Cutajar, and M. Filippone, “Autogp: Exploring the capabilities and limitations of gaussian process models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1610.05392*, 2016.
- [10] M.-C. Popescu, V. E. Balas, L. Perescu-Popescu, and N. Mastorakis, “Multilayer perceptron and neural networks,” *WSEAS Transactions on Circuits and Systems*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 579–588, 2009.
- [11] H. Salimbeni and M. Deisenroth, “Doubly stochastic variational inference for deep gaussian processes,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [12] K. Jakkala, “Deep gaussian processes: A survey,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.12135*, 2021.
- [13] A. G. Wilson, Z. Hu, R. Salakhutdinov, and E. P. Xing, “Deep kernel learning,” in *Artificial intelligence and statistics*, pp. 370–378, PMLR, 2016.
- [14] A. G. Wilson, Z. Hu, R. R. Salakhutdinov, and E. P. Xing, “Stochastic variational deep kernel learning,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 29, 2016.
- [15] M. Bauer, M. Van der Wilk, and C. E. Rasmussen, “Understanding probabilistic sparse gaussian process approximations,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 29, 2016.
- [16] C. K. Williams and C. E. Rasmussen, *Gaussian processes for machine learning*, vol. 2. MIT press Cambridge, MA, 2006.
- [17] A. Vaswani, “Attention is all you need,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.
- [18] A. Schmidt, P. Morales-Alvarez, and R. Molina, “Probabilistic attention based on gaussian processes for deep multiple instance learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 2023.
- [19] K. Chen and C.-G. Lee, “Attentive gaussian processes for probabilistic time-series generation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.05208*, 2021.

- [20] L. M. Bui, T. T. Huu, D. Dinh, T. M. Nguyen, and T. N. Hoang, “Revisiting kernel attention with correlated gaussian process representation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.20525*, 2025.
- [21] J. Hensman, N. Fusi, and N. D. Lawrence, “Gaussian processes for big data,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1309.6835*, 2013.
- [22] M. K. Titsias, “Variational learning of inducing variables in sparse gaussian processes,” *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 567–574, 2009.
- [23] M. Jankowiak, G. Pleiss, and J. Gardner, “Parametric gaussian process regressors,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 4702–4712, PMLR, 2020.
- [24] T. Rainforth, A. Kosiorek, T. A. Le, C. Maddison, M. Igl, F. Wood, and Y. W. Teh, “Tighter variational bounds are not necessarily better,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 4277–4285, PMLR, 2018.
- [25] M. Jankowiak, G. Pleiss, and J. Gardner, “Deep sigma point processes,” in *Conference on uncertainty in artificial intelligence*, pp. 789–798, PMLR, 2020.
- [26] Y. Li and R. E. Turner, “Rényi divergence variational inference,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 29, 2016.
- [27] X. Yue and R. Kontar, “The renyi gaussian process: Towards improved generalization,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.06990*, 2019.
- [28] J.-B. Regli and R. Silva, “Alpha-beta divergence for variational inference,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.01045*, 2018.
- [29] K. Wang, G. Pleiss, J. Gardner, S. Tyree, K. Q. Weinberger, and A. G. Wilson, “Exact gaussian processes on a million data points,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [30] X. Yue and R. Al Kontar, “Optimize to generalize in gaussian processes: An alternative objective based on the rényi divergence,” *IJSE Transactions*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 600–610, 2024.
- [31] M. Dehghani, S. Gouws, O. Vinyals, J. Uszkoreit, and L. Kaiser, “Universal transformers,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.03819*, 2018.
- [32] A. M. Braşoveanu and R. Andonie, “Visualizing transformers for nlp: a brief survey,” in *2020 24th International Conference Information Visualisation (IV)*, pp. 270–279, IEEE, 2020.
- [33] Q. Wang, B. Li, T. Xiao, J. Zhu, C. Li, D. F. Wong, and L. S. Chao, “Learning deep transformer models for machine translation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.01787*, 2019.
- [34] R. Sortino, S. Palazzo, F. Rundo, and C. Spampinato, “Transformer-based image generation from scene graphs,” *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, vol. 233, p. 103721, 2023.
- [35] C. Wu, F. Wu, T. Qi, B. Jiao, D. Jiang, Y. Huang, and X. Xie, “Smart bird: Learnable sparse attention for efficient and effective transformer,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.09193*, 2021.
- [36] M. Farina, U. Ahmad, A. Taha, H. Younes, Y. Mesbah, X. Yu, and W. Pedrycz, “Sparsity in transformers: A systematic literature review,” *Neurocomputing*, p. 127468, 2024.
- [37] M. Zaheer, G. Guruganesh, K. A. Dubey, J. Ainslie, C. Alberti, S. Ontanon, P. Pham, A. Ravula, Q. Wang, L. Yang, *et al.*, “Big bird: Transformers for longer sequences,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 33, pp. 17283–17297, 2020.
- [38] Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, H. Yuan, Z. Qin, Y. Yuan, Q. Gu, and A. C.-C. Yao, “Tensor product attention is all you need,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.06425*, 2025.
- [39] B. Qin, J. Li, S. Tang, and Y. Zhuang, “Dba: Efficient transformer with dynamic bilinear low-rank attention,” *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 2025.

- [40] H. Yuan, “Sha: sparse adaptive head of attention,” in *Fifth International Conference on Signal Processing and Computer Science (SPCS 2024)*, vol. 13442, pp. 436–441, SPIE, 2025.
- [41] D. Bahdanau, K. Cho, and Y. Bengio, “Neural machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.0473*, 2014.
- [42] V. Mnih, N. Heess, A. Graves, and K. Kavukcuoglu, “Recurrent models of visual attention,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 27, 2014.
- [43] Y. Wu, S. Kan, M. Zeng, and M. Li, “Singularformer: Learning to decompose self-attention to linearize the complexity of transformer.,” in *IJCAI*, pp. 4433–4441, 2023.
- [44] V. Lalchand, A. Ravuri, and N. D. Lawrence, “Generalised gaussian process latent variable models (gplvm) with stochastic variational inference,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.12979*, 2022.
- [45] L. Yann, “Mnist handwritten digit database,” *ATT Labs.*, 2010.
- [46] W. Zhu, “Classification of mnist handwritten digit database using neural network,” *Proceedings of the research school of computer science. Australian National University, Acton, ACT*, vol. 2601, 2018.
- [47] S. T. Roweis, “Nonlinear dimensionality reduction by locally linear embedding,” *Science*, vol. 290, p. 232, 2000.
- [48] G. Pleiss and J. P. Cunningham, “The limitations of large width in neural networks: A deep gaussian process perspective,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 34, pp. 3349–3363, 2021.
- [49] D. P. Kingma, “Adam: A method for stochastic optimization,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1412.6980*, 2014.

Appendix

A1. Renyi α divergence

In various fields of machine learning, the KL-divergence is often used to assess the distance between probability distributions. KL-divergence is a specific instance of the broader class of α -family divergences. A particular focus within the VI literature is the Renyi α -divergence. It is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_\alpha[q||p] &= \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} \log \int q(x)^\alpha p(x)^{1-\alpha} dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} \log \int q(x) q(x)^{\alpha-1} p(x)^{1-\alpha} dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} \log \int q(x) \left(\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} \right)^{1-\alpha} dx \\
 &= \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} \log E_q \left[\left(\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

The presence of the α enables us to adjust the strength of the bound to use. Setting α to 0 produces

$$D_0[q||p] = -\log \int p(x) dx = 0.$$

This indicates that we can obtain the maximum likelihood solution, meaning the bound is precise. When α is set to 1, we recover the KL divergence. By selecting a different value, we can create various behaviours that influence the type and tightness of the bound. Many of these concepts will be clarified later. If we take the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, we recover the KL-divergence given as $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1} \frac{1}{\alpha-1} \log \int q(x)^\alpha p(x)^{1-\alpha} dx$